

**The role, interdependencies and flows of added value between Central and Eastern Europe,
Germany, and China**

Ewa Cieřlik

Associate Professor

Poznan University of Economics and Business

Poland

Abstract

Central and Eastern Europe, Germany, and China have become close partners, especially in terms of trade and capital flows. The establishment of the EU-China Comprehensive Agreement on Investment (CAI) has proved to be an indispensable element that will provide the framework for future trade and investment cooperation. Unfortunately, the ratification of the agreement is hampered by the low protection level of the economic interests of the Central and Eastern Europe countries. They had little influence on the final shape of the agreement, hence there are many doubts about their role in EU-China relations, especially in high-tech production connections. This type of links turns out to be important in the era of introducing economies into the industry 4.0 phase. Thus, the task of the study is to understand the role, interdependencies and flows of added value between the closely related economies: China, Germany and the CEE region. The following research question was asked: with the intensification of CEE-China relations, have CEE economies become more involved in technological production links with China, at the expense of withdrawing from regional linkages?

Keywords: China, European Union, investment, trade

Introduction

The relations among China and the EU have become more closely and intensified. However, not all member economies or regions have been engaged in these relations at the same level. An attempt to achieve more equal access to one another market was the EU-China Comprehensive Agreement on Investment (CAI). At the end of 2020, China and the EU completed negotiations on CAI, the provisions of which go far beyond the investment activity itself. The possibility of CAI to enter into force has become an important aspect that could not only affect the cooperation between EU countries and China, but also have an impact on the shape of global production chains. From the perspective of the EU countries, signing the agreement would level the chances of European companies on the Chinese market. Ultimately, CAI would replace the 26 existing bilateral investment treaties between the EU and China, thus providing a unified legal framework. The core content of the agreement is based on specific EU requests to China for reforms and changes to investment regulations. The need to align the regulations on the activities of foreign companies with those in force in China, to protect investors and to refrain from discriminatory practices on the basis of nationality is underlined.¹ The perspective of the German economy (but also, to some extent, French and Dutch), which is the most closely connected with China in the entire EU, is clearly visible in CAI². Whereas, in negotiating the agreement, the perspective of smaller economies seems to have been lost (Elmer 2021)

Finding a balance in EU-China relations using CAI largely comes down to finding those industries and countries (or regions) where it is violated. Such a balance is especially needed by the CEE countries, which are becoming increasingly dependent on goods and services from China. The CEE economies, while being strongly connected with regional supply chains hub in Germany, rely

¹ According to the OECD's FDI Regulatory Restrictiveness Index, China imposes much stricter restrictions on FDI in services and manufacturing than EU countries (OECD 2022).

² It is estimated that in 2020, 30% of Chinese FDI reaching Europe were attracted by Germany. Eastern Europe accounted for 24% of China's FDI on the continent. The role of the UK is also growing, especially after Brexit in 2020 (12% of all Chinese FDI in Europe). Ultimately, the highest value of accumulated Chinese FDI in the years 2000-2020 was realized by the UK (EUR 51.9 billion), followed by Germany (EUR 24.8 billion) (Rhodium Group 2021).

heavily on foreign added value while providing relatively little of it themselves. Moreover, the situation is not improved by the fact that the largest CEE economies, including Poland, found themselves in a functional trap, i.e. the inability to exit from the role of a subcontractor responsible for less advanced stages of production in regional supply chains³ (Stöllinger 2021).

The role of CEE in global value chains is limited, which is reflected in the deteriorating production connections in recent years and ultimately the classification of the region in most manufacturing industries into the downstream market (relying more on foreign added value than making trading partners reliable on its added value) (Cieślik 2021). One of the ways of functional upgrading in manufacturing may be services treated as a component of final products (the so-called “servitization of manufacturing”). On the other hand, the preparation of countries to enter the industry 4.0⁴ phase indicates the need to develop advanced services. Taking into account the cost advantage of CEE, this would be an opportunity to strengthen its position in global production connections. The opening of the Chinese market in accordance with the conditions presented in CAI could theoretically turn out to be an opportunity for the CEE countries to upgrade their production connections by intensifying more advanced activities. However, in practice, CAI's influence on the development of CEE relations with China may turn out to be very limited, as it would not take place in a vacuum -

³ A similar view is confirmed by Pellényi (2020) research, which shows the gap in terms of employment in export sectors between the CEE countries and selected Western European economies. It turns out that CEE employs mainly fabrication and support employees, while R&D employees account for a negligible percentage. Moreover, the share of the latter has not increased significantly in recent years, which indicates the consolidation of the specialization in fabrication activities with low added value. Similar studies were carried out by Kordalska and Olczyk (2021 and Timmer, et al. (2019). They are more optimistic, as not all CEE countries have specialized in the stages of production with low added value. For example, Czechia and Slovenia are classified under R&D activities. However, the CEE economies are recording a deterioration in the relative positions in production connections, both in less and more advanced industries. Furthermore, they are losing importance in their flagship industries, such as automotive and electronics (Cieślik 2021a, b). This means that these economies have difficulties in upgrading production, as the EU markets with which they are most closely connected have assigned them to play an important role in less advanced stages of production (those that do not require knowledge-intensive tasks).

⁴ According to many studies, the CEE countries are not fully prepared for the transformation towards industry 4.0. In fact, the CEE region differs significantly from Western Europe in terms of R&D spending or the level of innovation (Eurostat 2021). ICT development and connectivity within global manufacturing connections are important milestones by which the region can adapt to the 4th industrial revolution. Currently, many indicators of the transformation of these countries towards industry 4.0 are still at a low level. For example, current education and training systems do not seem fully equipped to support the coming technological change, the number of ICT graduates remains low, the level of robotization is low and the number of patent applications differs from Western European countries. Naude, et al. (2019) used measures that reflect the three key dimensions of an economy's readiness for the fourth industrial revolution, namely technological, entrepreneurial and governance competences. They considered Czechia, Lithuania, Hungary and Slovenia as the readiest. Bulgaria, Slovakia, Romania and Poland were the least ready.

Germany and its relations with China play a significant role. The above line of reasoning formed the basis of this study.

The aim of the article is to understand the role, interdependencies and flows of added value between three closely related economies: China, Germany and the CEE region. Due to the problem of upgrading in production links in the CEE economies and the upcoming phase of industry 4.0, the study focused on ICT services and their subgroups. A method based on the study of value added streams was used. The study verified the following hypothesis: as CEE-China relations intensified, the CEE economies became more involved in technological production links with China, at the cost of withdrawing from regional ties.

The subject of the study are the CEE economies⁵, Germany and China. The method is based on an input-output model and analysis of foreign value added embodied in gross exports, while the statistical data comes from OECD's Inter-Country Input-Output (ICIO) Database. The scope of the study covers the years 2005-2018 (latest available statistics).

The study consists of four parts. The first one presents the general provisions of CAI, especially those related to technologically advanced markets. The second part is a brief introduction to the test method. The third part shows the production connections between China, CEE and Germany. The fourth part, on the other hand, focuses on information industries, especially ICT services, and their role in servitization of manufacturing. The conclusions answer the research question and indicate possible scenarios for CEE after CAI comes into force.

1. CAI Provisions: Key Aspects

In recent years, the EU has been losing heavily in terms of competitiveness against China, both in manufacturing and non-manufacturing activities (Turégano & Marschinski 2020) (Marschinski & Turégano 2019) (García Herrero & Turégano 2020). Moreover, all EU countries, except Ireland, have

⁵ For the purposes of this study, the countries understood as the EU-13 are: Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Malta, and Romania. However, in practice, the flows of value added with China are mainly generated by Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Bulgaria and Romania.

deep trade deficits with China (UNCTAD 2021). The European Commission explains this situation by the existing asymmetry in investor relations between economies - the EU has mostly opened its market, while China has not necessarily done the same (European Commission 2020). By giving wide access to the Chinese market, CAI may enable EU companies to enter more advanced sectors without the need to establish joint ventures and share profits with Chinese entities. It creates an opportunity to maintain control over technologies, to abandon its forced transfer practices and to improve the protection of intellectual property rights.

As presented in the official documents of the European Commission, CAI is the most ambitious agreement that China has ever concluded with a third country. This first agreement, which includes Chinese state-owned enterprises, will impose subsidy transparency and sustainability obligations. The EU is negotiating better access to Chinese markets and lifting quantitative restrictions, capital limits or joint venture requirements. Access conditions are to be transparent and independent of China's internal policy (European Commission 2020).

However, when looking more closely at the assumptions about access to the Chinese market, one may go as far as to say that CAI only formalizes access to sectors that China has already committed to opening. The agreement seems to aim to increase the protection and competitiveness of European companies against Chinese corporations (mostly state-owned) in the context of an increase of Chinese investment in the EU and a decrease of EU investment in China. Although Chinese investments in Europe are not significant in terms of statistics, some of them have been identified as 'politically sensitive', such as the takeover of the port of Piraeus, the Portuguese energy network or a robotic company in Germany (Bickenbach & Liu 2018).

CAI also includes a number of regulations related to counteracting forced technology transfer. Furthermore, China is expected to accept a broader definition of state-owned enterprises, ratify the ILO Forced Labour Conventions, and implement other organizational regulations. In the event of breach of contractual obligations, the parties will use the dispute settlement mechanism (European Commission 2020).

However, in practice, many difficulties may arise. For example, in the provision on the definition of state-owned enterprises it was forgotten that not all entities of this type in China are created equal. There are sovereign wealth funds, central and local state-owned enterprises, and state-owned enterprises in which the government has a share but which operate as private companies. Moreover, one should be aware that apart from the typical market motivations of state-owned enterprises, they are also tools supporting the state economic policy and introducing development strategies, e.g. the Belt and Road Initiative.

In turn, solving the problem of forced technology transfer requires more than just a change of law. It is associated with the requirement to implement complex and transparent regulations in China. The redefinition and reform of state-owned enterprises, mentioned above, will be needed to ensure their competitiveness in a more open market. Effective implementation of such regulations, if they are already in place, remains a controversial issue.

In the case of workers' rights, the adoption of the Convention on Independent Trade Unions and Collective Bargaining is questionable. There are also doubts about the enforcement of forced labour laws.

Although CAI covers many sectors (including the automotive sector, private healthcare, air and sea transport, etc.), some of the key industries are the more advanced ones, i.e. telecommunications, including cloud services, and computer services. In the case of the former, China has committed to lifting the investment ban for EU entities, subject to a 50% capital limit. However, in the case of computer services, it agreed to access the market and the introduction of the so-called technology neutrality, i.e. capital limits imposed on value added in telecommunications services, will not apply to other services when offered online (European Commission 2021).

Opening more advanced sectors to EU investments in China is aimed at gaining reciprocity, i.e. easing EU restrictions on Chinese investments. China has growing concerns about Europe's rising

opposition to its investments in the high-tech sector⁶. Moreover, the situation is worsened by the domination of the European high-tech sector by American companies. This strongly affects China's strategy for investing in developed countries, which focuses on technology and acquisitions to expand the market (Grieger 2020). Although the EU is quite open to FDI, the enactment of EU Regulation 2019/452 has established a framework for their monitoring. The regulations make it possible to stop FDI if it poses a threat to national security, public order or the environment (European Parliament 2019).

Unfortunately, in its current version, CAI does not resolve a number of important issues, especially for countries that are less developed than key EU economies. For example, the problem of small and medium-sized enterprises has been omitted, as the regulations on investments mainly apply to large projects carried out by market giants, of which relatively little exist in CEE (Polish Institute of International Affairs 2021). It should be remembered that some of the markets opened by China have already been dominated by domestic entities (e.g. Tencent and Alibaba control cloud services). Moreover, in terms of the level of technological advancement, Chinese companies more and more often outperform CEE entities, which will make it much more difficult for the latter to compete⁷. Subsidies are another issue on which China and the EU find it difficult to reach an agreement. Transparency of subsidies or other disruptive practices is an important gap that is not covered by WTO rules, but CAI is unlikely to solve them either (Dadush & Sapir 2021) (Hufbauer 2021). There is also the problem of separating state property from private property and determining what state support is and what aid can be considered excessive.

Finally, there is considerable uncertainty in the CEE countries as to the role of CAI, especially in view of their close connection with the German market and the intensifying relations between Germany and China. The agreement may particularly affect the most internationalized industries,

⁶ At the same time, China is increasingly swerving back and forth when it comes to European regulations. For example, Huawei will create a private 5G network for the Cambridge Science Park (owned by Cambridge University and headquarters of 120 technology companies) despite being blocked in the UK's national public infrastructure.

⁷ According to the "Business Confidence Survey 2021" 72% of respondents believe that Chinese companies are as or more innovative than European ones (Roland Berger 2021).

including automotive and electronics, in which CEE plays an important role. On the other hand, CAI would strengthen China's role in these industries, especially on the technological side. Hence, the fundamental question in the CAI debate is whether a tightening of relations between China and Germany would come at the expense of the CEE countries and how it will affect their role in production chains.

2. Method

The HIY method was used to examine the production links between CEE, Germany and China and to indicate the levels of dependence on the added value of individual economies. The input-output model used is a combination of the approaches developed by the following authors: Koopman, et al. (2014), Hummels, et al. (2001), Timmer, et al. (2019), and Timmer, et al. (2012), however, it extends their approaches to include cross-sectoral linkages. The method made it possible to calculate the content of foreign value added embodied in the exports of the surveyed countries. Details on the methodological approach can be found in the works of Cieřlik (2021a, b).

Data referring to trade in value-added statistics are collected by the OECD's Inter-Country Input-Output Database. The database provides information up to 2018.

3. General production links in the CEE-Germany-China triad

The regional supply chains built by Germany in CEE (especially in the Visegrad Group countries) allowed it to maintain a comparative advantage in sectors important for the economy, while helping the CEE countries to join global value chains, positively influencing economic growth, but also reducing them to entities operating in less advanced stages of production. Today, Germany also strongly cooperates with China, and the CEE economies are increasingly dependent on Chinese added value. In this way, a linkage triangle was created, especially in the automotive and electronics industries.

When analysing the CEE-China-Germany production connections, it is not surprising that the most intense flows among the analysed economies occur between Germany and the CEE. In general, there is an imbalance in all flows. However, the situation is slightly better in the case of the CEE-Germany and Germany-China ties. China has made Germany and CEE dependent on a similar level. Ultimately, 28.4% of CEE's production is based on added value from Germany and China, which is the highest dependence among the analysed economies. The opposite situation does not take place – the analysed partners do not rely as much (especially China) on the added value generated in the CEE region (diagram 1).

The introduction of CAI would aim to balance the presented flows. Germany and CEE would be particularly interested in increasing their share in the Chinese value-added market. On the other hand, China would probably further intensify the export of value added to EU manufacturing, but it is not certain whether it would still need CEE as a bridge economy in joining Western Europe and whether the resulting dependence of CEE on Chinese added value would not decrease.

Diagram 1

The CEE region is an important supplier of added value to German production. In 2018, 10.9% of the total foreign value added going to Germany came from the CEE countries (diagram 1). Wood and products of wood and cork (17.4%), as well as motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers (17.1%), warehousing and support activities for transportation (14.3%) were most strongly dependent on the added value from CEE. Also in other more technologically advanced industries, such as electrical equipment and machinery and equipment, n.e.c., the region's share in total foreign value added flowing to Germany was high (12.3% and 12.5% respectively). Based on the added value from the CEE region (mainly Poland, Czechia, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia and, to a lesser extent, Bulgaria and Croatia), Germany creates final products shipped to all over the world. Thus, the CEE economies, providing added value to Germany, join world trade through them (OECD 2022).

Looking at the opposite direction of flows in 2018, CEE relied on German added value in 20.8%, which made Germany the leader among individual suppliers (diagram 1). In these flows we

observed the largest share in motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers (30.6%) and rubber and plastics products (24.1%). Other sectors strongly associated with Germany were machinery and equipment, n.e.c. (23.9%), as well as paper products and printing (23.5% each) (OECD 2022). The added value going to the CEE region from Germany is often a component of semi-finished products used in German factories located in this area, which will eventually redirect these products to the headquarters in Germany.

In 2018, Germany remained less dependent on Chinese added value than on the added value from CEE (7.2% compared to 10.9%) (Diagram 1). China was the second most important individual supplier of added value after the United States. Chinese added value went primarily to the following industries: computer, electronic and optical products (16.6%), textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products and electrical equipment (12.8%), and electrical equipment (12.7%), where China played the role of a leader-supplier among individual economies. It should be noted that in the case of the automotive industry, China was a less important supplier of added value than CEE, but in comparison with individual economies it is ahead of individual countries in the region, being in the top-3 (OECD 2022).

Compared to Germany's dependence on Chinese added value, China's dependence is almost half that (diagram 1), giving Germany 6th place among individual countries in 2018 (only 4.5%). China relies on German value added mainly for the automotive sector (between 7.7-9.4% in the main group and subgroups). Added value also flows to electronics and machinery activities and pharmaceuticals, medicinal chemical and botanical products, but to a lesser extent (OECD 2022).

The flow of added value from CEE to China is of little importance (1.1%) and placed the region in one of the last places among suppliers (Diagram 1)⁸. Whereas, China made CEE strongly dependent on its added value (7.6%) (Diagram 1). Particular dependence is visible in computer, electronic and optical products (19.6%) as well as the main product group computers, electronic and electrical equipment (16.0%). Moreover, textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products

⁸ Most of the added value to China from CEE went to wood and products of wood and cork, which did not allow the region to rank high in this industry anyway.

(13.7%), electrical equipment (10.9%) and telecommunications services (11.7%) ranked China high among the providers of added value to CEE (OECD 2022). However, it should be remembered that a significant part of the added value imported from China goes to German factories located in CEE.

In total in 2018, CEE became the most dependent on China and Germany in computer, electronic and optical products (38.7%), motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers (37.5%) and the main product group transport equipment (37.1%) (OECD 2022).

4. Links within the information industries

Taking into account the industry 4.0 strategy introduced by the economies, one should pay particular attention to the phenomenon of the flow of value added coming from the group of the so-called information industries. Such activities will soon determine the country's position in global or regional production connections. In 2018, Germany relied on the added value from CEE only in 6.7% in the information industries, while the CEE region relied on Germany in 17.2%. The relations between Germany and China in these industries were even more unbalanced, as the former relied on Chinese added value in as much as 14.5%, while China depended very little on Germany (3.5%). In turn, CEE was based on the Chinese value added in 16.5%, while the share of CEE among the suppliers of this type of added value to the Chinese market was practically insignificant (diagram 2).

These flows clearly show asymmetry in market access – China restricts access to the broadly understood information industries, which can be seen in its low dependence on Germany and CEE, while the EU market accepts Chinese FDI in these industries and thus drives the inflow of added value. There is an even more complicated relationship in the interconnections within the information industries than in the general interconnections in the supply chains. CEE relies heavily on German and Chinese added value (33.7% in total), not being an important (especially in the case of China) supplier of added value and having difficulties in upgrading. Germany feels a deep imbalance in relations with China, which is directly related to FDI flows between the countries and supplying Chinese companies operating in Germany with semi-finished products, support services and hardware

from China. A similar situation occurs in CEE-China relations, but of a lesser intensity. CEE transfers its added value in the information industries to other countries through its German production connections, but it reaches the Chinese market to a very small extent. Therefore, CAI, by partially opening the Chinese information industries, could ease the imbalance.

Diagram 2

At the end of the discussion on information industries, it is worth pointing to the ways in which the value added from them flows between China and CEE. Usually there are three channels.

First, this type of added value flows through Chinese foreign investments, and the CEE countries are still perceived as quite attractive for Chinese investors (Cieřlik 2021). However, as it has already been mentioned, China is not among the most important investors in this region, as many times more investments come from Germany and other EU economies or the USA (especially when it comes to the CEE countries most strongly included in the global value chains). Often, these Chinese investments are related to acquiring technology and knowledge, as well as indirectly connecting with the German market. For example, Wahua Industrial and Huawei have invested in Hungary; Guanxi Liugong Machinery, Power Construction Corp. and Ex-Im Bank invested, and CITIC opened a branch in Poland, while CEFC established cooperation with J&T Finance in Czechia, and Hisense Group opened a factory in Slovenia. These companies rely heavily on technological solutions from China and are particularly active in importing end products and added value from the information industries.

Second, Chinese added value from the information industries comes through public procurement in the CEE countries. These economies have established technological cooperation with China, with Chinese technology often supporting clusters and telecommunications services. For example, Hungary is most involved in technological cooperation with China. Huawei won the tender to administer the emergency helpline. Moreover, the company claims to cover 2/3 of Hungary's total mobile equipment needs. ZTE offers internet services and plans to provide full 5G service (Global Times 2019). Chinese technology companies operating in Czechia include Changhong, Shanxi

Yuncheng Plating Group, Huawei or ZTE. The high position of Chinese added value in Czechia gross exports can also be explained by the cooperation (since 2015) between countries in the field of biotechnology and IT solutions (PrimeCell Therapeutics and SCL Biotechnology established a joint venture, SCL Biological Czech). Poland focused its cooperation with Chinese technology companies on consulting services, installation and maintenance of computer equipment, etc. Unofficially, there are almost 2/3 of NetWorkS! transmitters (T-Mobile Polska and Orange Polska, which is building a joint telecommunications infrastructure for the above-mentioned) based on Huawei solutions. Moreover, the Play network operating in Poland is based in 90% on the infrastructure of the Chinese giant in 5G (Telepolis 2020).

Third, Chinese added value within the information industries goes through foreign multinational corporations located in the CEE countries (mainly German). These multinationals import Chinese services and products directly from Chinese companies or branches of multinationals located in the PRC. Multinational companies deal with the import of technological equipment and software, as well as IT support in the automotive and electronic industries. For example, many automotive companies have set up plants in the CEE countries, incl. Volkswagen in Czechia, Hungary and Slovakia; Daimler in Hungary; Peugeot, Toyota and Kia in Czechia; General Motors in Poland; and Hyundai in Slovakia. These companies use many advanced products and services from China (e.g. components) that they apply in production. Global technology companies located in the CEE countries include: Foxconn Electronics Inc., Jabil Circuit Inc., Flextronics Corp., Elcoteq Network Corp., Royal Philips Electronics, Sony Corp., Bosch, Ericsson AB and Siemens AG. These corporations are, to a large extent, responsible for the greater dependence of the CEE countries on the Chinese value added from the information industries.

Within the information industries, one should look separately at the interrelationships of the triad of economies in servitization of manufacturing. These dependencies cause production upgrading and become an increasingly popular form of increasing the value of final products.

When analysing the dependence of CEE manufacturing countries on foreign added value from ICT services, the following phenomena can be seen. First, countries are increasing their dependence on foreign value added, which in the recent studied years has exceeded the domestic contribution to the servicing of manufacturing. Second, by far the strongest production connections in terms of servitization of manufacturing were observed within the EU-15, which in 2018 accounted for 61.1% of the ICT services included in the manufacturing activity (Germany played the most important role). Third, the role of the EU-15 in the servitization of manufacturing in recent years has been diminishing in favour of an increase in the share of economies such as China, which ranks highest among non-EU suppliers of added value to manufacturing (OECD 2022).

In 2018 in CEE, Germany was responsible for 14.8% (leader among individual countries), while China accounted for 3.1% (6th place) of servitization of manufacturing of ICT services. In Germany, 8.9% of servitization of manufacturing of ICT services came from CEE and 5.9% from China (6th place among individual economies). China was more dependent on German ICT services for manufacturing than those from CEE. Again, there is a large imbalance in the flows between CEE and Germany as well as CEE and China. The flows between Germany and China are more balanced. Ultimately, CEE was more dependent on German value added from ICT services than on China. Germany relied more on the added value from CEE, and China was more closely tied to Germany than to CEE (Diagram 3, Table 2).

Diagram 3

The following conclusions can be drawn from the analysis of the flows of value added from ICT services and their subgroups regarding manufacturing in the discussed triad of economies.

First, the servitization of manufacturing of Chinese ICT services has been growing rapidly in recent years. The increases in China's share are particularly visible in telecommunications in manufacturing as well as ICT services in computers, electronic and electrical equipment, and to a lesser extent in transport equipment. However, the responses of Germany and CEE to this phenomenon are different.

Second, two contradictory trends are observed - the role of German added value from ICT services in servitization of manufacturing and its subgroups in the CEE countries is clearly declining, while the role of CEE ICT services in servitization of German manufacturing is gradually increasing (however, it should be noted that these increases remain lower than in the case of the influx of value added from China). On the one hand, two phenomena lead to the mitigation of the imbalance in the flows of added value between Germany and CEE, and on the other, they may weaken the role of the CEE countries in German production connections and force the search for other partners.

Third, due to the very low and fluctuating shares of CEE ICT services used in Chinese manufacturing and its subgroups, the imbalance between China and the region is deepening.

The trends related to servitization of manufacturing and its subgroups of ICT services presented in Table 1 also show the separate approaches of Germany and CEE in shaping the flows of value added with China. Germany is trying to close the gap with China (without much success), making Chinese manufacturing more and more dependent on German ICT services, while at the same time controlling the incoming ICT services from China. However, the increase of German shares in the Chinese market with a certain capacity of companies means that Germany may reduce these shares in regional markets, which can be seen in the decline in the share of German value added in CEE.

Table 1

Despite the changes in value added flows presented above, the CEE region remains an important outlet for Chinese ICT services across the EU. However, in recent years, a decline in the importance of CEE and a return to shares has been observed from the beginning of the 21st century. Particularly high inflows of Chinese ICT services were observed in the period after the financial and economic crisis of 2008 (they even exceeded 90% in selected years). In 2018, CEE manufacturing absorbed 29% of the added value from Chinese ICT services, of which telecommunications in manufacturing accounted for 36.4%, and IT and other information services in manufacturing for 28.9%. China particularly favoured the computers, electronic and electrical equipment sector in CEE, which in the analysed period was used for most of the added value from ICT services directed to the

EU. However, the only industry in which the region's share in the entire EU has been growing in recent years is transport equipment, and these increases are generated by the aforementioned German automotive corporations (Table 2).

China ranks high among suppliers of added value from ICT services for manufacturing in the CEE countries. In the case of the servitization of manufacturing of telecommunications services and the servitization of computers, electronic and electrical equipment of ICT services, China is among the top 3 suppliers. In the analysed period, its position in the servitization of this industry was growing rapidly. It ranks slightly lower among ICT service providers for total manufacturing, but it is also in the top ten (OECD 2022).

Table 2

5. Conclusions

It is worth adding that the CEE economies are characterised by different perception of China – these countries are highly divergent and there is no unified identity in cooperation with China. According to (Suetyi and Yidong 2021) we can indicate four categories: “China-friendly” economies, in which Romania and Croatia belong, “China-neutral”, which includes three Baltic states and Bulgaria, “China-polarised” group, in which are Poland and Slovakia, and “China-sceptic”, which are formed by Czechia, Hungary, and Slovenia.

These polarized views derive from several factors. First, despite huge declarations, China has not invested and engaged in the CEE economies as much as it has presented in news. Moreover, these investments are directed in particular sectors what could be problematic for many governments (CEECAS 2021). Second, the format ‘17+1’ could have made bilateral trade more balanced, unfortunately, we have not perceived any signals of more balanced trade (UNCTAD 2021). Third, there is no consensus in terms of the Chinese influence in technological and security sphere. Finally, there are serious tensions from the EU for isolating China in the CEE economies. Recently, CEE-China relations have been deteriorating in general as Europe is more frustrated by the rise of China and the progress of Chinese-CEE relations is getting more disappointed. Moreover, the largest

economies in the EU have been complaining about China's activities in the CEE region. CEE economies within the format '17+1' have been accused of 'trading the political cohesion of the EU' for economic benefits from China. This impression is reinforced by the public communication and some political decisions (Matura 2021).

Generally, most of CEE countries are unsatisfied with the economic results of Chinese presence⁹. The above analysis confirmed that the CEE region's position in the important part of global economy, which is servitization of manufacturing of ICT services, has deteriorated in both ways. First, these economies have become more dependent on Chinese ICT services. Second, their contributions in Chinese manufacturing have not changed or in most cases even decreased.

The conducted research attempted to verify the hypothesis: with the intensification of CEE relations with China, CEE economies became more involved in technological production links with China, at the expense of withdrawing from regional ties. The presented data does not allow an unambiguous answer to confirm this hypothesis. The CEE countries are increasing their involvement in regional production links (in most cases, the share of their value added directed to Germany grew or remained unchanged), while a similar phenomenon is not observed in their relations with China - the shares of their value added fluctuate and remain at a very low level. However, the reduction in the role of CEE in regional value chains is visible after the reduction in the value added flowing to them from Germany (Germany, in turn, is increasing its involvement in the servitization of automotive and electronics in China, to some extent at the expense of CEE). On the other hand, China makes the CEE countries more and more dependent on their added value (although the importance of CEE compared to the entire EU is declining, mainly to the advantage of Germany), further deepening the imbalance in servitization of manufacturing of ICT services in the most internationalized sectors. A properly structured CAI agreement could redeem this situation, however, at least two scenarios related to the entry into force of CAI should be taken into account, the first of which seems to be more likely at the moment.

⁹ The interesting study on this presence prepared (Turcsányi 2020).

The entry into force of CAI would allow China and Germany to intensify the flows of ICT services (and information industries in general) and gain better access to their markets. There are mainly larger entities operating in the industries that are most closely connected with each other in the described triad regarding Germany and China. Whereas, there are often small and medium-sized enterprises that are subcontractors to German corporations in CEE. Signing CAI in the current wording would mean that in search of cost and technological advantages, some German corporations could give up regional connections (which is already visible) and move to China. Theoretically, the existing subcontractors from CEE could follow German corporations, but in practice it is difficult to talk about the possibility of entering the Chinese market by CEE companies, as in the industries that are being opened (according to CAI) they do not have a better chance against competitors (whether already functioning Chinese entities, or those just entering from Western Europe). For China itself, the added value from CEE does not matter much and can be quickly replaced with other suppliers. On the other hand, better access to the German market would mean that China would bypass the largest CEE markets (cease to be perceived as a bridge between China and Western Europe), continuing and deepening cooperation with the CEE countries outside the EU, i.e. Serbia, Montenegro, Albania, North Macedonia or Bosnia and Herzegovina. Nevertheless, it is already visible that the share of CEE in the inflows of value added from China to the EU is decreasing in order to service manufacturing. Ultimately, this would reduce the role of regional production connections in which the CEE countries participate and relegate these economies to the role of ad hoc providers of added value. Moreover, such a scenario would perpetuate their functional trap in production relationships.

The second scenario is more optimistic, however it would require not only changes to the CAI provisions, in order to better protect the interests of the economies closely related within regional supply chains, but also significant structural changes in the CEE countries. The CEE economies, aiming at more balanced relations with China and Germany, would have to significantly transform the export structure of the added value sent to the local market, i.e. make at least a partial upgrade

and move their economies faster to the industry 4.0 phase. It is possible that in this case, German corporations would not decide to transfer their production outside Europe, and then the CEE countries would maintain the role of an intermediary between China and Western Europe and continue to service German companies. This would increase their involvement in supply chains and not allow them to be marginalized. Such a scenario would require an agreement between the governments of the CEE countries, which would necessitate creating CAI provisions that take into account the specificity of their market (small and medium-sized enterprises, sub-suppliers dependent on one large recipient, lower level of technological advancement). In this scenario, apart from structural changes, also foreign policy and the attitude of entrepreneurs play an important role. One should also remember about the specificity of Chinese manufacturing, which relies to a much greater extent on its domestic added value than on foreign value and a growing tendency is observed in this respect. Furthermore, the CEE countries have to face fierce competition on the Chinese market, as the most important foreign suppliers of ICT services for Chinese manufacturing are the USA, EU-15 and East Asian countries.

There could be also the factor that disturb the above scenarios – COVID-19. Against the background of supply shortages during the pandemic and the conflict between the U.S. and China, reshoring of production has become an important issue in the world economy. The reshoring of production could be an opportunity for the CEE region. The economic and political justifications for reshoring is undisputable and it might improve the role of CEE in production links, especially with Germany. The GVCs could be shorter than pre-COVID-19 and the relations between Europe and China could become more balanced in terms of value added in favour of the CEE economies. However, this scenario depends on the ability of CEE to fulfil missing value added (supply bottlenecks) from China and other regions (European Parliament 2021) (Coface 2020) (European Commission 2021).

Regardless of the scenario that will take place, it cannot be denied that the CEE countries (especially the Visegrad Group, Romania, and Bulgaria) are important to China, as evidenced by their

inclusion in the Belt and Road Initiative corridors, the establishment of the '17 +1' or various initiatives aimed at intensifying the cooperation of the region with China. Moreover, on February 9, 2021, during the '17 +1' summit, the President of China recalled the importance of cooperation with CEE. The key words of his speech were: mutual respect, interconnectedness, unconditionalness, pragmatic and mutually beneficial cooperation, openness and tolerance, mutual benefits and beneficial results, technological innovation, climate change and green development. This allows presuming that China will not ignore the region in its relations with Europe. The question is how Germany will behave in this arrangement. In the face of these challenges, some experts perceive China's cooperation with the CEE region as destabilizing the unity of the EU¹⁰. However, the work on the entry into force of CAI testifies to the first step of the EU towards building a common strategy towards China and an attempt at geopolitical independence (in the context of relations with the US). In fact, in the current version, CAI would require a lot of fine-tuning sensitive aspects, which could significantly delay its entry into force. Moreover, in the work on CAI, the CEE countries should defend their interests more unanimously, as, depending on the scenario, they may be an aggrieved party or a winner of CAI.

Acknowledgment

The article is the result of the research project 'Digital Silk Road as a network of technological connections between China and Europe within value chains: towards win-win or decoupling?' financed by the National Science Centre, Poland (DEC-2021/43/B/HS4/01079).

References

Bickenbach, Frank and Liu, Wan-Hsin.. 2018. Chinese Direct Investment in Europe – Challenges for EU FDI Policy. *ifo Institute*, 19(4), pp. 15-22.

¹⁰ There were statements comparing these actions by China to the Trojan horse or attempts at conquering Europe (Karásková 2020) (Turcsáni 2014).

CEECAS. 2021, <https://www.ceecas.org/>.

Cieślik, Ewa. 2021a. "A New Era Is Beginning in Central and Eastern Europe: Information and Communication Technology Services Exceed Manufacturing in the Global Production Chain". *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*.

Cieślik, Ewa. 2021b. "Towards the industry 4.0: Have ICT services improved the position of Central and Eastern Europe in global production linkages?" *Manufacturing Letters*, pp. 11-16.

Cieślik, Ewa, 2021. "*Powiązania produkcyjne w wymianie handlowej między Chinami a Europą Środkowo-Wschodnią w dobie Belt and Road Initiative (Production links in trade between China and Central and Eastern Europe in the era of Belt and Road Initiative)*". Warsaw: PWE.

Cieślik, Ewa, Biegańska, Jadwiga and Środa-Murawska, Stefania. 2016. "The intensification of foreign trade in post-socialist countries and their role in global value chains". *Acta Oeconomica*, 66 (2), pp. 467-489.

Coface. 2020. "Post-pandemic production relocation: an opportunity for CEE countries" <https://www.coface.com/News-Publications/Publications/Post-pandemic-production-relocation-an-opportunity-for-CEE-countries>.

Dadush, Uri and Sapir, Andre. 2021. "Is the European Union's investment agreement with China underrated?" *Policy Contribution 09/2021, Bruegel*.

Elmer, Keegan. 2021. "*China-EU investment deal: smaller countries question whether France and Germany have their best interests at heart*", <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/diplomacy/article/3118009/china-eu-investment-deal-smaller-countries-question-whether>.

European Commission. 2020. *Key elements of the EU-China Comprehensive Agreement on Investment*, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_2542.

European Commission. 2021. *EU – China Comprehensive Agreement on Investment (CAI): list of sections*, <https://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/press/index.cfm?id=2237>.

European Commission. 2021. The Sectoral Impact of the COVID-19 Crisis An Unprecedented and Atypical Crisis, https://ec.europa.eu/info/system/files/economy-finance/eb069_en.pdf.

European Parliament. 2019. *Regulation (EU) 2019/452 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 March 2019 establishing a framework for the screening of foreign direct investments into the Union.*

European Parliament. 2021. Post Covid-19 value chains: options for reshoring production back to Europe in a globalised economy, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/653626/EXPO_STU\(2021\)653626_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/653626/EXPO_STU(2021)653626_EN.pdf).

Eurostat. 2021. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>.

García Herrero, Alicia and Turégano, David, 2020. "Europe is losing competitiveness in global value chains while China surges". <https://www.bruegel.org/2020/11/europe-is-losing-competitiveness-in-global-value-chains-while-china-surges/>

Global Times 2019. "Huawei, ZTE ink deals with Hungarian firms under BRI". <https://www.globaltimes.cn/content/1147635.shtml>

Grieger, Gisela. 2020. "International Agreements in Progress EU – China Comprehensive Agreement on Investment Levelling the Playing Field with China". *BRIEFING International Agreements in Progress*.

Hufbauer, Gary. 2021. *EU-China investment accord fails to resolve subsidy disputes*. <https://www.piie.com/blogs/trade-and-investment-policy-watch/eu-china-investment-accord-fails-resolve-subsidy-disputes>

Hummels, David, Ishii, Jun and Yi, Kei-Mu. 2001. "The Nature and Growth of Vertical Specialization in World Trade". *Journal of International Economics*, Issue 54, p. 75–96.

Karášková, Ivana. 2020. "Engaging China in 17+1: Time for the ACT Strategy". <https://thediplomat.com/2020/04/engaging-china-in-171-time-for-the-act-strategy/>.

Koopman, Robert, Wang, Zhi and Wei, Shang-Jin. 2014. "Tracing value-added and double counting in gross exports". *American Economic Review*, 104(2), p. 459–494.

Marschinski, Robert and Turegano, Martinez. 2019. "Reassessing the Decline of EU Manufacturing: A Global Value Chain Analysis". *Publications Office of the European Union*.

Matura, Tamas. 2021. "Chinese Investment in Central and Eastern Europe. A reality check", A Research Report by the Central and Eastern European Center for Asian Studies.

Naude, Wim, Surdej, Aleksander and Cameron, Martin. 2019. "The Past and Future of Manufacturing in Central and Eastern Europe: Ready for Industry 4.0?" *IZA Discussion Paper*.

OECD 2022. *OECD Stats*, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

Pellényi, Gabor. 2020. "*The Role of Central and Eastern Europe in Global Value Chains*". European Economy. European Commission.

Polish Institute of International Affairs 2021. *EU-CHINA COMPREHENSIVE AGREEMENT ON INVESTMENT: POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS FOR THE EUROPEAN UNION*, Warsaw.

Rhodium Group. 2021. <https://rhg.com/research-topic/china/#>

Roland Berger. 2021. *Business Confidence Survey 2021*

Stöllinger, Roman. 2021. "Testing the smile curve: functional specialisation and value creation in GVCs". *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, pp. 93-116.

Suetyi, Lai, Yidong, Cai. 2021. "Mapping perception of China in Central and Eastern Europe". *Asia Europe Journal*.

Timmer, Marcel, Miroudot, Sebastien and de Vries, Gaaitzen. 2019. "Functional specialisation in trade". *Journal of Economic Geography*, pp. 1-30.

Turcsányi, Richard. 2014. "Central and Eastern Europe's Courtship with China: Trojan horse within the EU?" *European Institute for Asian Studies*, Tom January.

Turcsányi, Richard. 2020. "China and the Frustrated Region: Central and Eastern Europe's Repeating Troubles with Great Powers". *China Report* 56, 1: 60–77

Turégano, David and Marschinski, Robert. 2020. "Electronics lead concerns over the EU's declining share in global manufacturing value chains".

<https://voxeu.org/article/eu-s-declining-share-global-manufacturing-value-chains>

UNCTAD 2021. *UNCTAD Stats*, <https://unctadstat.unctad.org/>

Diagram 1. Flows of added value between CEE, Germany and China in 2018 (share in total foreign value added)

Source: own calculations based on data (OECD 2022).

Diagram 2. Flows of added value between CEE, Germany and China in 2018 within the information industries (share in total foreign value added)

Source: own calculations based on data (OECD 2022).

Diagram 3. Flows of added value from ICT to manufacturing in CEE, Germany and China in 2018 (share in total foreign value added)

Source: own calculations based on data (OECD 2022).

Table 1. Flows of added value from ICT services and their subgroups to manufacturing in selected years (share in the total foreign value added; %)

	2005	2010	2015	2018	Change between 2018 and 2005
ICT services in manufacturing					
Germany → CEE	21.0	11.8	14.1	14.8	-6.2
CEE → Germany	6.9	8.6	9.9	8.8	1.9
Germany → China	5.2	5.8	6.9	2.8	-2.4
China → Germany	1.3	1.6	4	4.7	3.4
China → CEE	2.3	2.9	4.9	3.1	0.8
CEE → China	0.8	1.2	1.5	0.6	-0.2
Telecommunications in manufacturing					
Germany → CEE	17.8	14.3	11.7	10.8	-7.0
CEE → Germany	8.7	8.2	7.3	8.2	-0.5
Germany → China	3.5	3.4	3.1	1.5	-2.0
China → Germany	2.4	3.8	10.3	4.2	1.8
China → CEE	4.2	6.6	13.3	2.6	-1.6
CEE → China	0.8	1.0	1.1	0.4	-0.4
IT and other information services in manufacturing					
Germany → CEE	25.8	26.2	22.8	17	-8.8
CEE → Germany	4.9	8.9	11.9	9.8	4.9
Germany → China	8.5	8.8	10.4	3.2	-5.3
China → Germany	0.7	0.4	1.5	7.3	6.6
China → CEE	1.1	0.8	1.7	3.7	2.6
CEE → China	0.7	1.4	2.1	0.7	0.0
ICT services in transport equipment					
Germany → CEE	29.4	27.0	23.0	20.5	-8.9
CEE → Germany	8.3	10.2	12.0	10.6	2.3
Germany → China	8.9	9.1	8.1	4.2	-4.7
China → Germany	1.2	1.5	4.0	5.4	4.2
China → CEE	1.2	1.6	4.4	3.0	1.8
CEE → China	1.0	1.6	1.8	0.9	-0.1
ICT services in computers, electronic and electrical equipment					
Germany → CEE	16.9	17.8	18.6	15.1	-1.8

CEE → Germany	6.6	8.8	10.1	8.6	2.0
Germany → China	4.6	5.5	7.6	2.6	-2.0
China → Germany	2.5	3.6	7.8	8.4	5.9
China → CEE	4.9	6.5	9.4	6.0	1.1
CEE → China	0.7	1.1	1.5	0.6	-0.1

Source: own calculations based on data (OECD 2022).

Table 2. Share of the CEE countries in the Chinese added value flowing to the EU in 2005-2018 (%)

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
ICT services in manufacturing	33,6	34,3	40,0	42,5	45,7	46,2	36,5	30,7	29,2	30,4	28,3	29,5	29,9	29,0
Telecommunications in manufacturing	35,8	34,4	38,9	40,5	48,4	45,1	39,7	37,2	34,3	36,1	35,0	36,4	37,0	36,4
IT and other information services in manufacturing	33,4	35,2	41,7	45,2	48,5	50,2	38,4	30,8	29,7	30,4	27,9	29,1	29,9	28,9
ICT services in computers, electronic and electrical equipment	65,7	62,6	78,3	82,3	96,7	97,6	82,2	69,6	62,3	62,4	56,1	56,3	55,7	53,7
ICT services in transport equipment	27,5	32,1	36,8	37,9	40,2	36,6	31,9	27,9	29,1	33,0	33,2	35,0	36,0	35,4

Source: own calculations based on data (OECD 2022).